

**DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS INTERRELATIONSHIP WITH INCREASING THE
COMPETITIVENESS OF REGIONS BY IMPROVING PRODUCT PROFITABILITY
EVALUATION**¹Ismailova M.M, ²Ergasheva B.N^{1,2}Oriental University<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142845>

Abstract. Market has grown in terms of its products, quantities and quality, increasing its competitiveness, increasing exports, and promoting foreign economic relations with foreign exchange earnings. Many modern enterprises are being put into operation in our country, new jobs are created, the income of legal and physical entities is growing, advanced business management methods and innovative entrepreneurship activities going to the decision as well.

Key words. Digitalization, competitiveness, product, profitability, regions economy.

As a result of the wide-ranging reforms undertaken in the country, sustainable development is being achieved in the national economy. The domestic market has grown in terms of its products, quantities and quality, increasing its competitiveness, increasing exports, and promoting foreign economic relations with foreign exchange earnings. Many modern enterprises are being put into operation in our country, new jobs are created, the income of legal and physical entities is growing, advanced business management methods and innovative entrepreneurship activities going to the decision as well. An in-depth synchronization of such positive changes has led to a more rapid growth of the national economy.

It should be noted that the changes taking place in the economy are influenced by many factors at different levels. Despite the fact that the extent of the effect factor is large or small, whether important or not, each of them has a role in the outcome change. Establishment of production of highly productive products in the business activities of enterprises is also an important factor in the development of economic entities. This factor plays a major role in the sustainable development of the economy both at micro level (both enterprise) and macro (scale of businesses). One of the priorities of reforms in the country is the implementation of measures aimed at accelerated development of finished products with high added value based on deep processing of local raw materials. So, the right thing to do is one of the most important tasks of today.

The role of literature in the production of highly productive products in the enterprises is also important. Because, through the methods and methods used in the literature, the effectiveness of the product is determined on a scientifically-based basis, is predicted, planned, calculated, controlled, and analyzed economically. Finally, production activities are effectively managed and managed according to the product of high efficiency or effectiveness. Observations show that in the sectoral literature, the effectiveness of the product is determined on the basis of different approaches and methods. It should be noted that the indicators proposed on the basis of specific approaches, in terms of their designation, determine which aspects of economic efficiency are reflected and their practical significance. However, rapid and dramatic change of economic relations in our time makes it necessary to take immediate account of their demands. This requires a specific framework or settlement objects and procedures for measuring and evaluating relationships and outcomes. Contemporary approaches are of particular importance as they are aimed at ensuring the correctness of the effectiveness of new relationships. That is, in the case of traditional methods, there is a lack of attention or deficiencies. Alternatively, new computational

objects and procedures are proposed based on innovative ideas. As an example of our vision, let's just say one of the factors that determines the effectiveness of the enterprise's business. In practice, profitability is different from other types of performance, which reflects the need for profitability, role and significance. The profitability indicator is assigned to report a certain level of profitability over the reporting period relative to a particular account object (typically spent production costs, assets, equity, etc.). This determines the effectiveness of the particular account object relative dimensions and evaluates its effectiveness or efficiency. The profitability indicator is widely used both in the international arena and in the national accounting system. It should be noted here that the profitability indicator is divided into several types by definition. For example, the overall asset profitability, profitability of fixed assets, profitability of current assets, private equity profitability and so on. However, while profitability indicators differ in their names and content, they remain essentially of one type. Taking into account that it is not possible to bring profitability indicators into the same system and to cover their needs or weaknesses within the same article, we would like to express our viewpoint in the example of product profitability.

In the business activity, the product profitability indicator shows the effectiveness of a certain product, and hence the degree of its usefulness. That is, it answers the question of how much the profit or cost of a product spent on the production of goods is profitable. However, our observations have revealed that in the literature and in the field of applied farming, there are many cases where adequate attention is paid to the correctness of the product profitability. In addition, it was found that there were serious shortcomings in the operating procedures for determining product profitability. The existence of different approaches to this issue among economical scientists makes it more difficult to reach a coherent solution.

Formulas are used to calculate the productivity or productivity of the product, the level of profitability of the product, only based on the information pertaining to a particular reporting period.

In calculating the financial contribution of capital (investment) expenditure, each information relating to the period for investment activity is received in the form of a general assembly and is calculated using the formulas. For example, five years have been set for investment activities. Thus, the five-year data of the cost of production or cost of production is formulated in aggregate form.

One of the perspective directions in this direction is the study of profitability based on cash flow. Calculation and the proper management of cash withdrawal in business activities are a crucial requirement of the present time.

Combining profitability indicators in enterprise business, economic analysis is a necessary measure. Because economic analysis is an integral part of enterprise business.

Based on our findings, it is desirable to analyze the productivity profitability indicators in the following order:

1. Separate and generalized analysis of the profitability indicators of the company, based on the types of production in the production activities;
2. Evaluate dynamic changes in profitability indicators in product development activities;
3. Factor analysis of changes in profitability indicators in product production;
4. Finding resources that will affect the profitability of product development.

All the above-mentioned ideas can be summed up in the conclusion that enterprises are always in need of the economy, which is always based on business efficiency and based on market-oriented market transition. Properly detect and analyze profitability indicators and utilize their data

effectively remains one of the most important guidelines for business administration. When the industry's experts anticipate and understand them through event-related events or events that occur in their economic relationships, they can be avoided by the potential risks involved. This means the proper direction of business activities.

REFERENCE

1. Industrial and Regional Clusters: Concepts and Comparative Applications (second edition: c2000). by Edward M. Bergman and Edward J. Feser (PDF with commentary at wvu.edu)
2. Computable General Equilibrium Modeling for Regional Analysis (c1999), by Eliécer E. Vargas, Dean F. Schreiner, Gelson Tembo, and David W. Marcouiller (PDF with commentary at wvu.edu)
3. An Introduction to Regional Economics (fourth edition; c1999), by Edgar Malone Hoover and Frank Giarratani (PDF with commentary at wvu.edu)
4. 21st Century Cooperation: Regional Public Goods, Global Governance, and Sustainable Development (London and New York: Routledge, c2017), ed. by Antoni Estevadeordal and Louis Wolf Goodman (PDF with commentary at oapen.org)